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**Adverse drug events of immune checkpoint
inhibitors - a retrospective, descriptive real-world
data analysis**

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Publikation

Adverse drug events of immune checkpoint inhibitors - a retrospective, descriptive real-world data analysis

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Abstract

Aims: The objective of this study was to analyze immune-related adverse events (irAEs) in a real-world data sample and examine the differences in incidence between affected organ systems, irAE severity, therapeutic agent, and gender.

Methods: We retrospectively analyzed all consecutive patients treated with anti-cytotoxic T-lymphocyte associated protein 4 (CTLA-4) antibodies, anti-programmed death 1 (PD-1) inhibitors, and programmed death-ligand 1 (PD-L1) inhibitors between January 2020 and May 2023 in a tertiary referral center in Switzerland. IrAEs documented in the electronic health records (EHR) were graded according to the Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE) and analyzed descriptively.

Results: Among the 500 patients, 196 (39.2%) were female. Treatments included pembrolizumab (51.2%), atezolizumab (20.2%), nivolumab (14.4%), durvalumab (6.4%), ipilimumab in combination with nivolumab (4.8%), cemiplimab (1.4%), avelumab (1.2%), and ipilimumab (0.4%). N = 216 (43.2%) patients had ≥ 1 irAEs (females: 47.4%; males: 40.5%). Severe (\geq grade 3) irAEs were reported in 13.6% of patients. The following irAE incidences were found: dermatological (15.2%), gastrointestinal (13.0%), endocrine (10.8%), musculoskeletal (4.8%), pulmonary (3.8%), systemic (3.6%), neurological (2.6%), cardiac (1.4%), renal (1.4%), hematological (0.6%), and ocular (0.2%).

Conclusion: Nearly half of the patients experienced ≥ 1 irAEs, of which one-third severe. Females experienced more irAEs than males, above all due to a higher incidence of grade 1 irAEs. Only about half of the irAEs were reported as coded diagnosis. Further prospective studies on irAEs are warranted using structured documentation.

1. Introduction

Cancer therapy is a central field of medical research due to cancer being one of the leading causes of death worldwide. Immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs), including anti-cytotoxic T-lymphocyte-associated protein 4 (CTLA-4) antibodies, programmed death 1 (PD-1) inhibitors, and programmed death ligand-1 (PD-L1) inhibitors, are new treatment options that have improved survival rates for some cancers significantly [1]. CTLA-4 and PD-1 are receptor proteins on T-cells that are involved in the autoregulation of the immune system. PD-L1 is a receptor protein that binds to PD-1 on antigens. Tumor cells can use these receptors to reduce an anti-tumor immune response. Blocking these receptors enhances the immune response to tumor cells. The exact molecular pathways are complex and not yet fully understood [2,3].

There are several indications for ICIs, such as melanoma, hepatocellular carcinoma, and lung cancer where ICIs can dramatically improve survival in some patients groups [4]. One of the major challenges in ICI therapy is the occurrence of immune-related adverse events (irAEs). The literature on the incidence of irAEs is heterogeneous. Reported irAEs incidences for CTLA-4 inhibitors range from 14.87% [5] to over 80% [6]. Reported irAE incidences for PD-1 Inhibitors and PD-L1 inhibitors range from less than 1% to approximately 71.8% depending on the agent [5,7,8]. Overall, PD-1 and PD-L1 inhibitors appear to have a similar toxicity profile for all-grade irAEs and cause fewer irAEs than CTLA-4 inhibitors. For grade 3-5 irAEs, PD-L1 inhibitors appear to be safer than PD-1 inhibitors [7,8]. The combination of two ICIs provokes significantly more side effects and seems to be even less safe than chemotherapy in terms of adverse events [7]. While the incidence of irAEs is high with ICIs, the risk of treatment-related death is estimated to be 0.45%-2.5% [8,9]. The time to onset of irAEs depends on the agent, the treatment regimen and the organ affected, with a median time to onset of 6-8 weeks after starting therapy [10,11]. However, irAEs can also occur weeks to months after completion of therapy [11].

IrAEs may occur in one single or in multiple organ systems. Common irAEs include rash, pruritus, nausea, diarrhea, and thyroid dysfunction. Less common but potentially fatal irAEs include pneumonitis, encephalitis, hepatitis and myocarditis [10,12]. A list of irAEs [10,12–14] is provided in *Table S1* as supplementary material. Most studies use the Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE) [15] to classify the severity of irAEs. The CTCAE distinguishes five grades of adverse events. Grade 1 defines no to mild symptoms without any need for intervention, grade 2 moderate symptoms with need for minimal, local, or non-invasive intervention, grade 3 severe symptoms but not life-threatening complications, grade 4 life-threatening consequences, and grade 5 adverse event-related death.

Until now, most studies investigating irAEs of ICIs were conducted as phase IV clinical, prospective observational studies or analyses of adverse-event reporting databases. To our knowledge, little is known about the significance of irAEs in a real-world sample.

Aim of the study

The aims of this study were (1) to gain insights into the occurrence of irAEs while receiving ICI treatment in a real-world setting, (2) to examine differences in irAE incidence between affected organ system, irAE severity, therapeutic agent and gender.

2 Methods

2.1 Study design and study patients

We performed a retrospective, monocentric, observational study involving patients treated at the Lucerne Cantonal Hospital (hereafter referred to as the study center). This study center is a tertiary referral hospital in central Switzerland with approximately 50,000 inpatients and more than 900,000 outpatient contacts per year, that offers all medical specialties except organ transplantation. We included inpatients and outpatients of the study center aged ≥ 18 years old treated with a CTLA-4 antibody (ipilimumab), a PD-1 inhibitor (nivolumab, pembrolizumab, and cemiplimab), or a PD-L1 inhibitor (atezolizumab, avelumab, and durvalumab) between January 1, 2020, and May 31, 2023. Exclusion criteria were refusal to provide informed consent for use in scientific research, inaccessible medical records, and initiation of therapy before January 1, 2020. In addition, we excluded patients with loss to follow-up between January 1, 2020, and May 31, 2023, and patients who received non-simultaneous different ICI agents with an interval of less than 12 months because we could not have assigned an occurring irAE with certainty to one agent. Data of eligible patients were extracted from their electronic health records (EHR). The protocol was approved by the local ethics committee (BASEC No 2023-01292) on August 10, 2023.

2.2 Procedures

2.2.1 Data collection

Initial extraction of eligible patients was performed by the study center IT team. Patient data included age, sex, cancer type, ICI agent used, total number of treatment cycles, duration of treatment, diagnoses, and date of death if deceased. ICI agents included monotherapies with ipilimumab, nivolumab, pembrolizumab, cemiplimab, avelumab, durvalumab and atezolizumab as well as the combination-therapy ipilimumab combined with nivolumab. In a second step, data on irAEs –site, grade, date of occurrence- were collected from physician and nurse notes in electronic medical records. If a patient experienced multiple irAEs, then all irAEs were counted. Regarding the severity of symptoms only the highest grade was used. Information on concurrent therapies, such as radiotherapy or chemotherapy, was not collected because different therapy protocols were used from patient to patient, which would result in too small subgroups. The extracted data were entered into a REDCap database and pseudonymized.

2.2.2 Patient subgroups and classification systems

Patient diagnosis was coded with the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems 10th Revision (ICD-10-GM) [16]. We first translated the codes into cancer types [16]. We then grouped the cancer types based on the ICD-10-GM chapters (Table S2).

The collected irAEs were assigned to the ICD-10-GM code following the guidelines provided by ICD-10-GM and classified according to the site of manifestation and severity. The site of manifestation was summarized into the following groups (*Table S7*): neurological, ocular, endocrine, pulmonary, cardiac, gastrointestinal, renal, muscular, skeletal, dermatological, hematological, and systemic. Severity was classified according to the CTCAE version 5 [15].

2.3 Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics provided an overview and a better understanding of the occurrence of irAEs. Patient and disease characteristics grouped by ICI agents, as well as by the presence or absence of irAEs were summarized as medians and interquartile range for continuous variables, and as counts and percentages for categorical variables. The distribution of irAEs in organ systems and of irAEs grades (1-5), partly grouped by ICI agent, were statistically and visually described. Differences between genders were also represented visually with various bar plots. Statistical analyses were conducted in R (version 4.4.1.; R Foundation for Statistical Computing) [17], and graphs were realized with Excel (version 2409) [18].

3. Results

3.1 Participants

Of the 554 ICI records selected based on the inclusion criteria and extracted from the EHR of the study center system, 500 were included and analyzed (*Figure 1*). A separate record was created for each ICI used. For combination therapy involving two ICIs, two records were generated. As a result, a single patient could have multiple records. 54 records were excluded for three different reasons. First, 24 patients appeared twice in the ICI records because they received simultaneously ipilimumab and nivolumab. These 48 records were combined into 24, creating a combination-therapy group “ipilimumab + nivolumab”. Second, 14 patients receiving therapies with two or more ICIs with an interval of <12 months between therapies were also excluded, resulting in 29 excluded records. Third, one patient representing one record had to be excluded because of loss to follow up due to a change of hospital after the first dose.

Figure 1: Record flow-chart

3.2 Patient characteristics

Of the 500 patients included, 304 (60.8%) were male and 196 (39.2%) were female (*Table 1*). The median age was 67 years (IQR 58-74). The most used agent was pembrolizumab with n = 256 (51.2%), followed by atezolizumab with n = 101 (20.2%) and nivolumab with n = 72 (14.4%). Of all patients, 32 (6.4%) were treated with durvalumab, 24 (4.8%) with ipilimumab + nivolumab, 7 (1.4%) with cemiplimab, 6

(1.2%) with avelumab, and 2 (0.4%) with ipilimumab. Patients were treated with ICIs for the following cancers; “lung cancer or cancer of other intrathoracic organs” (n = 210, 42.0%), “cancer of digestive organs” (n = 73, 14.6%), “skin cancer” (n = 67, 13.4%), “cancer of the urinary tract” (n = 53, 10.6%), “breast cancer” (n = 30, 6.0%), “head and neck cancer” (n = 26, 5.2%), “cancer of female genitals” (n = 19, 3.8%), “cancer of soft tissue and mesothelioma” (n = 12, 2.4%), “other cancer sites” (n = 4, 0.8%), “cancer of male genitals” (n = 0.6%), and “cancer of lymphoid, hematopoietic and related tissue” (n = 3, 0.6%).

Table 1: Patient characteristics (N = 500)

ICI Class	CTLA-4 inhibitor	PD-1 inhibitors			PD-L1 inhibitors			Combination CTLA-4 + PD-1 of inhibitors	
Parameter	Ipilimumab	Pembrolizumab	Nivolumab	Cemiplimab	Atezolizumab	Durvalumab	Avelumab	Ipilimumab + Nivolumab	Total
Total, N (%)	2 (0.4)	256 (51.2)	72 (14.4)	7 (1.4)	101 (20.2)	32 (6.4)	6 (1.2)	24 (4.8)	500
Age, median (IQR)	51.0 (48.5 to 53.5)	67.0 (58.0 to 74.0)	64.0 (55.0 to 72.0)	81.0 (70.0 to 86.5)	66.0 (60.0 to 73.0)	73.5 (61.8 to 77.0)	72.5 (71.2 to 76.0)	61.0 (52.5 to 72.5)	67.0 (58.0 to 74.0)
Sex, N (%)									
Female	0 (0.0)	106 (41.4)	22 (30.6)	4 (57.1)	40 (39.6)	15 (46.9)	1 (16.7)	8 (33.3)	196 (39.2)
Male	2 (100.0)	150 (58.6)	50 (69.4)	3 (42.9)	61 (60.4)	17 (53.1)	5 (83.3)	16 (66.7)	304 (60.8)
Cancer Location, N (%)									
Lung and intrathoracic organs ¹	0 (0.0)	122 (47.7)	4 (5.6)	0 (0.0)	60 (59.4)	24 (75.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	210 (42.0)
Digestive organs ²	0 (0.0)	18 (7.0)	33 (45.8)	0 (0.0)	14 (13.9)	8 (25.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	73 (14.6)
Skin ³	2 (100.0)	34 (13.3)	10 (13.9)	4 (57.1)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	17 (70.8)	67 (13.4)
Urinary tract ⁴	0 (0.0)	24 (9.4)	16 (22.2)	0 (0.0)	6 (5.9)	0 (0.0)	6 (100.0)	1 (4.2)	53 (10.6)
Breast ⁵	0 (0.0)	24 (9.4)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	6 (5.9)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	30 (6.0)
Head and neck ⁶	0 (0.0)	19 (7.4)	4 (5.6)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (12.5)	26 (5.2)
Female genitals ⁷	0 (0.0)	10 (3.9)	0 (0.0)	3 (42.9)	6 (5.9)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	19 (3.8)
Soft tissue and mesothelioma ⁸	0 (0.0)	2 (0.8)	4 (5.6)	0 (0.0)	3 (3.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (12.5)	12 (2.4)
Other	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	4 (4.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	4 (0.8)
Male genitals ⁹	0 (0.0)	1 (0.4)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (2.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (0.6)
Lymphoid, haematopoietic and rel. tissue ¹⁰	0 (0.0)	2 (0.8)	1 (1.4)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (0.6)

Corresponding ICD-10-GM codes: ¹C30-C39; ²C15-C26; ³C43-C44; ⁴C64-C68; ⁵C50; ⁶C00-C14 & C69-C72; ⁷C51-C58; ⁸ C45-C49; ⁹C60-C63; ¹⁰C81-C96

3.3 Main results

3.3.1 Incidence and spectrum of irAEs

Of the 500 patients, 216 (43.2%) had one or more irAEs documented in their medical records (*Table S8*). Among female patients (n = 196), 93 (47.4%) had one or more irAEs, while among male patients (n = 304), 123 (40.5%) reported at least one irAE. The median age of patients with irAEs was 66.0 years (IQR 56.7-74.0) and 67 years

(IQR 59.0-74.2) for those without irAEs. 154/500 patients (30.8%) experienced one irAE, 47/500 patients (9.4%) two irAEs, and 13/500 patients (2.6%) three irAEs. In total, 287 irAEs were reported. The cancer type with the highest irAE incidence was the “other” category with 75% (n = 3/4) which is not representative when considering the small sample size. The cancer type with the highest incidence and an analyzable sample size was skin cancer with 56.7% (n = 38/67), followed by head and neck cancer with 50% (n = 13/26).

The highest irAE rate of 100% (n = 2) was observed with ipilimumab (*Figure 2, Table S3*), however, this rate is not representative due to the small sample size. The second highest rate was found for ipilimumab + nivolumab with 83.3% (n = 20/24). The irAE rates for the other ICIs were as follows: avelumab, 50% (n = 3/6); durvalumab, 46.9% (n = 15/32); pembrolizumab, 42.6% (n = 109/256); nivolumab, 40.3% (n = 29/72); atezolizumab 35.6%, (n = 36/101) and cemiplimab, 28.6% (n = 2/7).

Considering the organ systems, the most common irAEs were dermatological with an incidence of 15.2% (n = 76/500), followed by gastrointestinal with 13% (n = 65) and endocrine with 10.8% (n = 54). Lower rates of irAE were seen for the musculoskeletal (4.8%, n = 24), pulmonary (3.8%, n = 19), systemic (3.6%, n = 18), neurological (2.6%, n = 13), cardiac (1.4%, n = 7), renal (1.4%, n = 7), hematological (0.6%, n = 3), and ocular (0.2%, n = 1) organ systems.

Regarding severity (*Figure 2, Table S3*), the incidences for documented irAEs were: grade 1 (mild) 10%; grade 2 (moderate) 19.6%; grade 3 (severe) 12.8%; grade 4 (life-threatening) 0.6%; and grade 5 (death) 0.2%.

Considering the different ICIs used, dermatological irAEs were more common with PD-L1 inhibitors (9.9-33.3%) and ipilimumab + nivolumab (33.3%) than with PD-1 inhibitors (14.1-15.3%). Gastrointestinal irAEs were predominantly seen in the ipilimumab and ipilimumab + nivolumab group (37.5-100%). The incidence of endocrine irAEs was higher with ipilimumab and ipilimumab + nivolumab (25-50%) than with PD-1 inhibitors (5.6-11.7%) and PD-L1 inhibitors (7.9-15.6%). Musculoskeletal irAEs were similarly distributed among the agents (4-9.4%) except for avelumab, for which a rate of 33.3% was reported, and cemiplimab as well as ipilimumab, for which no musculoskeletal irAEs were reported. Pulmonary irAEs were most common under pembrolizumab treatment (4.7%), but with only small differences to the other agents (2.8-4.2%). Systemic irAEs were primarily observed with cemiplimab and ipilimumab + nivolumab (12.5-14.3%), while very low incidences were reported in the PD-L1 group (0.0%-3.0%). Nivolumab had the highest incidence among neurological irAEs (6.9%), followed by ipilimumab + nivolumab (4.2%). All other agents showed rates below 3.1%. Cardiac irAEs were mainly caused by

cemiplimab and ipilimumab + nivolumab (14.3% and 12.5%, respectively), while all other agents had incidences below 1.0%. Renal irAEs were observed using nivolumab (2.8%), pembrolizumab (1.6%) and atezolizumab (1%). Hematological irAEs were caused by ipilimumab + nivolumab (4.2%) and pembrolizumab (0.8%), and ocular irAEs by nivolumab only (1.4%).

Figure 2: Number of patients with irAE per agent and severity. For detailed information please refer to Table S3 in the supplementary materials.

3.3.2 Severe irAE

Severe (\geq grade 3 according to CTCAE [15]) irAEs occurred in 13.6% ($n = 68$) of patients treated with ICIs (Figure 3, Table S5). Of all severe irAEs, 94.1% ($n = 64$) were grade 3, 4.4% ($n = 3$) were grade 4, and 1.5% ($n = 1$) were grade 5. The two patients who received ipilimumab both had severe irAEs, resulting in a rate of 100%. Ipilimumab + nivolumab caused severe irAEs in 45.8% of the patients, cemiplimab in 14.3%, nivolumab in 13.9%, pembrolizumab in 13.7%, atezolizumab in 6.9%, and durvalumab in 3.1%. No severe irAEs were reported with avelumab. The organ system distribution differs from all-grade irAEs (Figure 3). While 13.7% of all patients had one or more dermatological irAEs, only 0.8% had a severe dermatological irAE. The most common severe irAEs were gastrointestinal with an incidence rate of 4.4% and pulmonary with 3.0%. There were no severe systemic or ocular irAEs.

Figure 3: Number of reported irAE per organ system and grade. For detailed information please refer to Table S5 in the supplementary materials.

Severe irAEs included: ¹generalized skin eruption (n = 3), erythroderma (n = 1); ²drug induced liver injury (n = 16), colitis (n = 4), cholecystitis (n = 1), pancreatitis (n = 1); ³diabetes mellitus (n = 2), hypopituitarism (n = 2), adrenocortical insufficiency (n = 1); ⁴arthrodynia (n = 1), myalgia (n = 1); ⁵acute interstitial lung disorder (n = 13), chronic interstitial lung disorder (n = 1); ⁶toxic encephalopathy (n = 5), myasthenia gravis (n = 2), retrobulbar neuritis (n = 1); ⁷myocarditis (n = 4), cardiomyopathy (n = 1), paroxysmal tachycardia (n = 1), pericardial effusion (n = 1); ⁸nephropathy (n = 5), acute renal failure (n = 1), chronic kidney disease (n = 1); ⁹haemolytic anemia (n = 1), leukocytosis (n = 1)

3.3.3 Gender differences of irAEs

One or more irAEs occurred in 47.4% (93/196) of female patients and 40.5% (123/304) of male patients. The distribution of irAEs across organ systems was similar in male and female patients (Figure 4). Only one organ system was more frequently affected in male than in female patients. Musculoskeletal irAEs was present in 5.3% (n = 16) of the male patients against 4.1% (n = 8) of the female patients. The greatest difference in irAE grade was seen in grade 1 irAEs (Figure 5). 13.8% (n = 27) of the female patients experienced grade 1 irAEs compared to 7.6% (n = 23) of male patients. Grade 2 irAEs occurred in 19.4% (n = 38) of females and 19.7% (n = 60) of males, grade 3 irAEs in 13.3% (n = 26) of females and in 12.5% (n = 38) of males, grade 4 in 0.5% (n = 1) of females and 0.7% (n = 2) of males, and grade 5 in 0.5% (n = 1) of females, while no grade 5 irAE was documented in male patients. Further details are shown in Table S6 in the supplementary materials.

Figure 4: irAE incidences per organ system and severity

Figure 5: severity of irAE comparing females vs. males

3.3.4 Documentation of irAEs

In 56.1% of patients with irAEs, we found documentation in the ICD-10 GM diagnosis list of EHR. In 44.9% of patients, irAEs were documented only in the medical notes.

4. Discussion

In this study, we analyzed retrospectively documented irAEs associated with CTLA-4 inhibitors, PD-1 and PD-L1 inhibitors in a real-world sample. The overall all-grade irAE incidence was 43.2%. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses have reported higher overall all-grade incidences of 66% [8] and 66.4-96.8% [7], respectively. When considering the agents individually, we also found an all-grade irAE incidence lower than what is frequently reported in the literature. In a meta-analysis by Xu et al. [7], the pooled incidence of all-grade irAEs was 75.1% for pembrolizumab (vs 42.6% in our study), 71.8% for nivolumab (vs 40.3%), and 66.4% for atezolizumab (vs 35.6%). In a systematic review, Arnaud-Coffin et al. [19] observed incidences similar to Xu et al. [7]. However, a more recent analysis of the Food and Drug Administration adverse event reporting system by Chen et al. [5] found lower irAE incidences than ours. The all-grade irAE incidence was 92.91% for ipilimumab + nivolumab, 23.18% for pembrolizumab, 49.9% for nivolumab, 7.09% for atezolizumab, and less than 1.0% for avelumab and cemiplimab. Consistency between our study and the existing literature can be seen in the ranking of ICI agent classes. In our study, the combination therapy ipilimumab + nivolumab showed the highest incidence of irAEs. As only two patients were treated with ipilimumab monotherapy in the present study, the irAE incidence of 100% cannot be considered reliable [7,20]. The lowest incidence of irAEs was seen with cemiplimab and atezolizumab. Other studies ranked combination therapies with two ICIs as less safe than one ICI alone [7] and ranked PD-1 and PD-L1 inhibitors as safer than CTLA-4 inhibitors [20] [7] [21].

The most common irAEs were dermatological, with an incidence of 15.2%. This is low compared with existing literature. Muhaj et al. [22] reported incidences of 18-34% for PD-1/PD-L1 inhibitors. Heinzerlingen et al. [23] and Kim et al. [24] also outlined dermatological irAEs as the most common ones with incidences of 46.0-62.0% and 43.2%, respectively. After dermatological irAEs, gastrointestinal irAEs were the second-most frequent irAEs (13.0%) in the present study. Arnaud-Coffin et al. [19] found incidences between 12-60% for colitis and diarrhea, depending on the substance used, which represented the fourth highest type of irAEs after systemic, dermatological and pneumological irAEs. Heinzerlingen et al. [23] found gastrointestinal irAEs as second-most frequent irAEs with incidences of 22-48%, depending on the substance used. We observed endocrine irAEs in 10.8% of patients. Kim et al. [24] described a much higher incidence of 30.7%, while Yoo et al. [25] mentioned an incidence of all endocrine irAEs of 18.7% in a meta-analysis. While we found incidences below 10% for all other irAE groups, in Kim et al. [24] and Arnaud-Coffin et al. [19], both pulmonary and rheumatological irAEs occurred in more than 10% of patients. Some studies have hypothesized that dermatological and gastrointestinal irAEs are so frequent because of the high immunological activity in the skin and intestines. However, there is no conclusive research yet that can explain the

different incidences among the affected organ systems, as the molecular pathways of irAEs are still being studied [26,27].

There are several aspects that may have led to the inconsistencies in incidences. Notably, Xu et al. [7] mostly analyzed clinical trials, whereas Chen et al. [5] analyzed adverse event reporting system data, and in our study, we analyzed hospital data. Ramos-Casals et al. [28] mentioned that some discrepancies between different studies may be related to the inclusion of non-specific symptoms such as rash and arthralgia, that are not necessarily immune-mediated. In our study, we included such symptoms only in case of first occurrence under ICIs. Other potential reasons for discrepancies include differences in ICI doses, patient monitoring, irAE classifications, and follow-up time [29]. In addition, some irAEs rely on patient self-reporting, which may be influenced by factors such as trust in the physician or cultural behaviors. Especially with mild symptoms, it is not unusual for patients to consult the general practitioner, who will only refer them to a specialist, if the reaction is not manageable. Furthermore, it is not possible to estimate the number of reported but non-documented irAEs. Mild irAEs without therapeutic consequences that would have been documented in clinical trials may not have been documented in the medical records, as the clinical importance of those reactions is low in multimorbid or palliative patient, in whom other symptoms had a dominant impact on their condition. Another consideration is that patients often received concurrent radiotherapy or chemotherapy that we did not account for. Some irAEs may have been misattributed to other therapies or considered tumor-related, as therapeutic consequences are often similar (e.g., symptomatic treatment of pruritus). This lack of standardization makes comparison with the existing literature difficult and requires more detailed reviews in future research, comparing standardized irAE groups in patients treated with the same ICI agent.

Two thirds (68.5%) of the reported irAEs were categorized as grade 1-2, and one third (31.5%) as grade 3-5. We observed differences between agent classes. PD-1 and PD-L1 inhibitors classes caused irAEs of grade 3 or higher irAEs in about 14% or fewer of the patients taking these specific ICIs, whereas CTLA-4 inhibitors and ipilimumab + nivolumab caused such events in more than 45%. Other studies found similar incidence trends. Arnaud-Coffin et al. [19] found \geq grade 3 irAEs in 14.6% (vs. 0-13.9% in the present study) of patients treated with PD1/PD-L1 inhibitors and 55.1% (vs. 45.8%) in patients treated with immunotherapy combination. Xu et al. [7] found \geq grade 3 irAE incidences as follows: pembrolizumab 19.8% (vs. 13.7% in the present study), nivolumab 14.1% (vs. 13.9%), and atezolizumab 15.1% (vs. 7.9%). Wang et al. [8] reported in a meta-analysis that 14% of patients treated with PD-1 and PD-L1 inhibitors showed \geq grade 3 irAEs. Furthermore, we found a mortality rate of 0.2%, in meta-analyses and systematic reviews, rates between 0.45-1.3% were reported. [8,19].

In this study, females had a higher incidence of irAEs than males, with most of the difference attributable to grade 1 irAEs. One reason for this difference could be that

females more often report adverse events than males, as observed in an analysis of adverse event reporting by Watson et al. [30]. This could be especially important for low-grade irAEs that are not assessed or observed spontaneously by the clinician. The distribution of the irAEs in the organ system was similar between females and males. Chen et al. [31] published similar results, except for renal toxicities which seemed to be more frequent in males. In addition, they found a higher proportion of deaths in males. However, another study found the opposite, reporting significantly higher incidence rates and a lower median overall survival time for females. [32] and a meta-analysis [33] found only minimal differences in irAE incidence between females and males. More studies with standardized subgroups are needed in order to compare the incidence and severity of irAEs between sexes.

For 45% of patients with irAEs, the irAEs were not documented in the diagnosis list, but only in medical notes of EHR. As there is no standardized approach for clinicians to document irAEs, the method of documentation may vary between healthcare professionals. Moreover, limited time may affect the quality of documentation. A study by Leung et al. [34] investigated the influence of structured reporting of adverse events in patients undergoing radiation therapy. They report significant differences in documentation quality with and without the structured grading tool, without additional time effort. However, there was no significant difference in patient-reported outcomes. Although the effect of structured documentation of irAEs on outcomes is unclear, their documentation is crucial for future real-world studies. Reporting templates in hospital software should be implemented in the clinical routine.

There are several proposals for monitoring and reporting irAEs with detailed algorithms. In clinical trials, irAEs are usually graded according to the CTCAE [15], which is used in this study. However, the assessment of the CTCAE criteria is challenging to implement in a real-world setting, especially in retrospective studies. Another grading score, the adverse event burden score (AEBS), has been proposed by Le-Rademacher et al. [35]. It considers not only the maximum severity of adverse events that occurred, but also their frequency. In addition, the patient-reported outcomes version of the CTCAE (PRO-CTCAE) has been developed [36]. In a Delphi study, Da Silva Lopes et al. [37] proposed a list of relevant irAEs by reconciling several expert opinions in addition to the symptoms included in the PRO-CTCAE. Naidoo et al. [38] proposed classification of irAEs according to natural history (recurrent, delayed/late and chronic), pattern (multisystem), and response to irAE treatment.

These various reporting instruments reflect the lack of definitive consensus on reporting and the significance of irAEs, even among experts. Taken together, the use of the CTCAE grading system in daily clinical practice is challenging given the limited time, resources, and lack of training of clinicians. Despite its limitations in retrospective grading the CTCAE grading system is the most widely used and therefore provides the best comparability between studies.

Strengths and limitations

To our knowledge, this is the first study with real-world data examining the whole spectrum of irAEs including all ICIs available in Switzerland in. This study has several limitations, including its retrospective design making it impossible to derive any causality. In addition, the retrospective grading of irAEs is challenging and carries the risk of misclassification. Furthermore, due to the monocentric design of the study, the results may not be generalizable to other populations. Data was collected from medical records, which may result in subjective and incomplete reporting. The variable size of ICI subgroups represents another limitation. The absence of data on concurrent therapies, such as radiotherapy or other chemotherapies, or the total dose of ICIs may have introduced bias into the data collected.

5. Conclusion

Nearly half of patients in this real-world sample experienced one or more immune-related adverse events (irAEs). Of all irAEs, about one third were severe (\geq grade 3). Females showed a higher incidence of irAEs than males, primarily due to a higher incidence of grade 1 irAEs. This study revealed no trends indicative of gender disparities of irAEs across different organ systems. In almost half of the patients, IrAEs were not documented in the correct section of the EHR. Further research is required to assess the occurrence of IrAEs. Such research should be conducted using prospective studies that implement standardized protocols.

List of abbreviations

AEBS	Adverse Event Burden Score
CD	Cluster of Differentiation
CTCAE	Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events
CTLA-4	Cytotoxic T-Lymphocyte Associated protein 4
EHR	Electronic Health Records
ICD-10-GM	International statistical Classification of Diseases and related health problems: tenth revision – German Modification
ICI	Immune Checkpoint Inhibitor
irAE	immune-related Adverse Event
PD-1	Programmed Death-1
PD-L1	Programmed Death-Ligand 1

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

From all patients included in this study written informed consent was obtained, allowing us to analyze the data from their electronic health records and to publish data anonymized. All analyzes were performed retrospectively. No experiments on humans or use of human tissue samples have been performed. This study meets the regulatory requirements of the HRA (Human Research Act) and HRO (Human Research Ordinance) of Switzerland.

The protocol with the with the BASEC No 2023-01292 was approved by the local ethics committee (“Ethikkommission Nordwest- und Zentralschweiz”) on August 10, 2023.

Consent for publication

Not applicable

Availability of data and materials

The data analyzed in this study are available from authors on reasonable requests.

Competing interests

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

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Authors' contributions

All authors contributed to the study conception and design. Material preparation and data collection was performed by L.A. and B.H. Data analysis was performed by all authors. The first draft of the manuscript was written by L.A. and all authors commented the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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